

Management of NGO's -A Case Study on CODP, Mangaluru

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ABSTRACT

Non-Governmental Organizations(NGOs) play an important role in various development issues across the world. In view of the increasingly important role of the voluntary sector in the development process, the NGOs face lot of challenges in their management and developmental challenge. In the past, the word 'Management' was considered as business management, but for NGOs, it was taken negatively in the sense of commercial operations. There has been development of NGOs in understanding the importance of management, and also the executives to reason over the issues of vision, mission, goals, strategic planning, effective coordination and communication, human resource management etc. However, the search for the definition of distinct management for this sector is underway. By considering existing literature need is felt to study the management of NGO's thus in this paper as concerned a case study of Canara Organisation of Development and Peace(CODP) is done by considering their overall management aspects. SWOT analysis is also done in this paper about general management.

Key words: NGO's, NGO Management, CODP

Introduction:

The human being tends to live in groups and in society because it is the society that protects one's socio-economic and political interests. It is in light of protecting these interests that people struggle either individually or in groups and through some organisations. People had natural phenomena to organise themselves into families, clans, tribes, ethnic groups and communities from the very beginning even before any government existed. People were assiduous to solve their problems, shared what they had in common and worked in groups. Everywhere, they had natural and locally accepted modes of solving their problems, organising community work, helping the poor, supporting the arts and managing religious duties.

Presently, NGOs have taken the form of organisations as national or international institutions working outside the public administration of the country. The NGOs undertake developmental research, program preparation and service delivery at the intermediate and local levels. The NGOs include a variety of agencies and institutions such as cooperative,

professional and social organisations, clubs and associations, research institutions, charitable, religious and neighbourhood groups throughout the country.

About NGO

A Non-Governmental Organisation means- a team of people with similar interest, freely joining hands to bring about improvements or changes in society through organised and collective efforts. the term Non-Governmental Organisation is actually a misnomer. They act as the Liaison between people and the governments.

The appropriate and finest definition can be: " An independent, autonomous and vibrant sector which can work on social and development problems of the country with the freedom that the Government Institutions do not have and a sense of commitment and concern for the people, that the business sector does not much care for".- (Rajesh Kothari) NGOs work for the development of the nation through involving in various subjects like- Education, Health, Livelihood, Micro -finance, Human rights and many more. It is up to the NGO to choose issues on which they want to work for.

About General Management

Management is the process of planning, staffing, directing and controlling to accomplish objectives through the coordinated use of human and material resources. One of the important social activities has been 'managing' since people began forming groups to achieve their aims and objectives which they could not get as individual.' Irrespective of the nature of organisation, managing has been essential in order to ensure its effectiveness and productivity. As society has come to depend increasingly on group efforts as many organized groups, private or public, have become large. The development of management includes setting objectives, designing the methods and creating an environment for the application of designed methods in order to achieve the set objectives. The scope of management greatly varies because of the variations in the nature of organisation - private, public and voluntary.

About Management of NGO's

Although the NGO sector has established itself as third sector of society along government and business, still the management thoughts and systems are in developing phase. However, the positive development in this reference is that the debate on the distinctiveness of the feature, character and functions of the sector is over and now the academicians and practitioners are exchanging thoughts over development of distinct management system on the basis of the distinctness of the sector. Whatever, the discussions in the forms of speeches and writings are going on, no doubt much valuable, but these are still being considered as the initial work in this reference and not become the part of NGO Management literature.

The history of writings and speeches over NGO Management is not very old. It is recent phenomenon. For the last fifteen years, the NGO world has been thinking over to design the management system of NGOs distinct from the management of private (Cos) and public organisations (GOs).

There is no specific definition of NGO Management up till now. Rather the concept of general management is prevailing in this sector. However, in the context of NGO Management, one attempt at a definition that came up during this research, which was quoted by Piers Campbell and developed during the seminar on 'NGO Management Development and Training' held at Tagacity, Phillipines as "Management emphasises the concept of working with and through others and making effective use of the available resources in order to achieve the organisation's goals and objectives".

Literature Review

Performance management in the non-profit sector has not been widely studied in comparison to for-profit organizations. Performance measurement is variedly defined in non-profit literature. The definitions cited in the literature include “project performance evaluation” (Poister, 2003), “evaluation of individual, group and organisation performance” (Ferreira and Otley, 2009), “monitoring economy, efficiency, effectiveness and efficacy” (Fine and Snyder, 1999; Teelken, 2008), “monitoring workload and productivity” (Ammons 1996), “outcome measurement” (Wainwright, 2003; Benjamin and Misra, 2006; Moxham, 2009) and “program evaluation” (Zimmerman and Stevens, 2006; Carman, 2007; Miller, 2007). For Not-for-Profit Organizations, there are various frameworks that measures program-specific performance or individual performance or multidimensional that considers both the programs and individuals. Program-specific frameworks focus on the measurement of program inputs, impacts done by the programs, outcomes and outputs from the programs, while Multidimensional models measures diverse effectiveness and performance domains. Community Based Organisations are Non Profit Organizations (NPOs) owned by the community itself. NPOs are operated in small scale with limited financial resource and small-scale operations with a mission to provide social empowerment and promote advocacy.

Need for the study

Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) play an increasingly important role in different fields like environment, development and uplifting human causes and poverty alleviation through education and economic empowerment of women, youth through self-employment and vocational trainings. NGO take a greater role in decision making have a greater impact on policy implementation of government programmes, take a supportive role to mobilise people, and bring about the awareness about a problem and benefits to the right beneficiaries.

This study is an attempt to explore all aspects that go into management of NGOs, its functioning, to know how they implement programmes through its members and staff and their reach to needy people. It also would like to study the problems faced by them, the limitations they have while providing service to the needy, and the problem they face internally and from external forces such as donor pressure and governmental pressures. At the end an attempt will be made to give a few suggestions which may be useful for NGOs to implement to increase their competence and achieve excellence in their specialised and interested areas of operation and activities.

Objectives of the study

1. To assess the organisational structure of NGOs for their effective functioning
2. To analyze means and methods of information dissemination and their empowerment programmes.
3. To understand the challenges faced by the CODP, Mangalore in the organisation and administration of their activities
4. To study the network of authority/responsibility relationship in CODP Mangalore

Research Methodology

This paper is focusing on the case study of CODP, a NGO where general management and its working data were gathered from published sources. The annual reports which is of secondary data and at the same to understand the existing research in the field. Thus books, journals and magazines are referred. On account of primary data discussions were held with NGO Manager and workers to understand the ground reality of planning process, organization structure and working style.

CODP Mangalore – A Case Study

It was a time when India was facing so many problems, which caused a severe effect on the economic development of our country. The hindrances were nothing but population explosion, poverty, unemployment etc., as a result young youths of the county were at a disappointing stage and there was also a sharp decrease in humanity among people by understanding this trend, Fr. Edwin Pinto decided to do something for the betterment of the country. Finally on 16th April 1974 he established a Non-Governmental Organisation at Nanthoor with different objectives. Canara Organisation for Development and Peace is committed to the development activities. It undertakes in underdeveloped areas of Dakshina Kannada and Udupi districts of coastal Karnataka and Kasaragod districts of Kerala in India.

History repeats itself - but always with a difference! It is a silent beginning somewhere by someone, it is a lightning intuition received by a few chosen ones, it has always been the unnoticed. Bloodshed of pioneering few that has brought about the evolutionary mutation involving progress and development.

The C.O.D.P. was registered on 16.4.1974 under Mysore Societies Regulation Act 1960. It was founded by Most Rev. Basil S. D'Souza in 1974. CODP is located in the urban surrounding of Nanthoor at Mangaluru, Karnataka state. The organisation is located at a distance of 3 KMs from the city of Mangaluru.

Operational Area's

Self -Help Groups:

- * The SHGs significantly contribute to the empowerment of its members, especially women.
- * It provides a savings/credit mechanism which suits the needs of its members.
- * Acts as a forum to solve individual/common problems through self help or mutual help.

Table 1.1 Profile of SHG

1	Total SHGs	685	No. of Mahasanghas	43
2	Total Membership	9,133	No. of Taluk Federations	6
3	Savings – Rs	5,08,65,901/-	No. of Dist Federations	1
4	Loan advanced - Rs	10,26,37,124/-	No. of self managing SHGs	265
5	IGP/Self-employed	1,537	SHGs using ILMS method	284
6	Micro finance to the tune of Rs 1,22,30,000/- availed by 813 women			

(Source: Annual report)

Education Programme:

Assistance for Higher Studies

- * Rendering financial support to the poor but intelligent students to pursue higher studies.
- * Enhancing the intellectual capacity of the student community through motivation programmes.

Table 1.2 Education Programme

Activities	Course taken up	Students
1) Few students and 36 students of the previous years were provided with financial assistance, to continue their education.,	B.A, B.Com, B.Ed, BBM, B.E, B.Sc	39
	Nursing QNM, PC 13:Sc Nursing	17
	M.A., M.B.A., M.Com., M.S.W., M.Sc., M.Tech.,	13
2) A. get-together and 3 motivation programmes on “Self-esteem and Civil Services” were held in Oct. and Dec. 2013. In all 46 students participated.	M.Sc Nursing, C.A. ITI, Dip. in Ophthalmic Tech., Dip. in Electrical and Electronics, Fine Arts, Hotel Management, Company Secretary.	6

(Source: Annual report)

Educare: Supported by Dubai based Mangalorean NRI philanthropist:

- * To provide interest-free loan to the poor students of Mangaluru and Udupi Dioceses.
- * Talk on 'Motivation and guidance to join government jobs' and 'Self-esteem' was arranged for students in 12 batches.

Environment Programme:

1. Food Security and Livelihood Improvement

- * This project is directed to guide and assist rural farmers in promoting soil and water conservation measures, thereby ensuring the quality of life and livelihood.
- * The planned course of activities during the year was: Promoting sustainable organic farming, Strengthening of the Milk Dairy unit, Strengthening of VDC and formation of SHG Federation.

Table 1.3: Empowerment programmes and results:

Sl. No	Programmes	Results
1.	Awareness and Training programmes	10 trainings conducted - 379 farmers and community people participated: Concept of organic fanning, Marketing skills and seed selection, Seed Bank, Milk Collection Centre, maintaining quality subsidy and other benefits, Result Based Approach, Bank linkage & Micro Finance. - 60% of the farmers are either using good quality seeds or/ and organic manure in their fields. - Production of milk has increased from 160 liters to 220 liters.
2.	Exposure visits	2 exposure visits - 28 farmers participated: To the organic farm of Mr Anthony Joseph at Permai and Krishi Mela (Agriculture Fete) organised by SKDRDP®, Moodabidri.
3.	Soil/Water conservation measures	- 8 vermi compost tanks constructed - 6 jeevamrutha units set up 13 bio-gas units established

(Source : Annual Report)

Health:

Sneha Hiv/Aids Project

- * To develop community based intervention and rehabilitation aimed at enhancing the quality of life and life expectancy of PLWHA.
- * To reduce high prevalence of HTV/ AIDS.
- * This programme is phased out in Dec. 2013

Table 1.4 Health

Sl. No	Particulars	Total No
1.	PLHIVs and CLHTVs identified	81+24
2.	TB cases identified	43
3.	Referral Services: ART/VCTC/TB Centre/ Care and Support Centre/ Govt./Pvt hospitals, etc.	650
4.	Home visits by co-ordinators/animators in 3 years	Over 3000
5.	Awareness/Sensitisation programmes and special events	54
6.	Training/orientation for stake holders in the target areas	13
7.	Support services: Nutritional/Medical/Skill training/IGP	376
8.	Govt/Private schemes-NGO programs availed by PLHIV & family members	170
9.	Funds mobilized from SHGs/Govt/PRI/Private/Instts., etc	Rs 2,34,090

(Source: Annual report)

1.5 Table Profile of CODP

Address	Nanthoor, next to Padua College Mangaluru
Name of the founder	Most Rev. Basil S. D'Souza
Year of Establishment	1974
Registration Detail	3/74-75
Taluk / Districts -Locations	5-10
Branches of the organisation	Mangaluru- 2 State-Kerala-1

Table 1.6 : Programmes and Special focus areas

Related to Education	1
Awareness programmes on Health	5
Self employment & Vocational training	2
Sanitation & Hygiene	4
Women Empowerment	1
Awareness on human rights	8
Girl child Safety	6
Service for the old aged	7
Agriculture - support systems	2
Natural resource management	3

The above table describe CODP is doing a yeomen service to humanity. It is found that they are more involved in uplifting human lives, empowering, and supporting in sectors like education, agriculture, self-employment/vocational training, and sanitation found to be of top priority. While women empowerment, girl child safety, natural resource management, awareness on human rights and services for the old age are also taken up in right earnest.

Women Empowerment, Education, Self employment and Vocational training, Agriculture - support systems, Natural resource management, Sanitation and Hygiene, and Awareness programmes on Health as their first 5 top priorities as activities.

In Discussion with leadership and employees of **CODP**, study found they give higher priority to –Women empowerment and education. Under Women empowerment, they have formed self-help group's who have been supported and trained on various activities for their upliftment and provide Loans. For education, they provide study loans and scholarship to deserving students from primary to higher education.

Table: 1.7 Organisational Structure and Style

Organisational structure	Functional
Leadership style	Democratic
Performance Report To	Government,Board of Directors General Body,Registrar of societies

Study opinion is that – every planning aspect and the needs of beneficiaries differ and some of them are dependent on Government funding and others on the NGOs fund which is from their internal accruals. An individual even though he is the visionary leader of the NGO, he may not be privy for complete information of recipients, whereas in a democratic style of functioning as observed by **CODP** it becomes a collective decision after verifying all facts, records and relating them to vision and objectives of the organisation. Hence, a democratic style of functioning will be transparent and you can avoid any bias.

CODP ,reports to registrar of society and governed by Societies registration act 1960, their donors to get 80G benefit and they report to ministry of foreign affairs as they are covered under Foreign Contribution Regulation Act, 2010.

Table: 1.8 Functioning of the Organisation

Frequency of Planning	Fortnightly
Number of employee	
Top	7
Middle	30
Lower	7
Remuneration	
Top	Rs. 15,000 & below
Middle	Rs. Above 10,000
Lower	Above 5,000
Method of communication	Personal Contact, Newspaper, Website, Booklet, Announcement at the Church
Invite people from other NGO's	Yes
Service training to employees	Yes
Duration of the training period	
Top	Less than one week
Middle	Less than one week
Lower	Nil

The style adopted by **CODP**, which is fortnightly planning looks practical as they follow democratic system. All concerned people know the decisions, can guide others in the implementation of the plans, and can review which may need some changes in the next fortnightly meeting.

“SWOT Analysis”

Organisational strategies are the means through which companies accomplish their missions and goals. Successful strategies address four elements of the setting within which the company operates and you need to identify them in right earnest:

- The organisational strengths
- Organisational weaknesses
- The opportunities organisations foresee in its competitive environment
- The threats organisations may face in their competitive environment.

Strengths:

- Experienced staff
- Specialised Project staff
- Service Brand is well Established
- Infrastructure & sponsors support

A priest who functions as a director and management member heads **CODP**. He is full of enthusiasm, believes in people participation and in decision-making process and is friendly listens to their suggestions and in many programmes he gets involved and supports the staff. It also found **CODP** has kept excellent relationships with media and their programmes get maximum coverage and this has created excellent reach out. In addition, it found very senior people who have great experience in this field are associated with them and they contribute their might in conducting the activities.

Weaknesses:

- Limited Funds
- Limited Resources
- Employee attrition
- RBI Regulations
- Gender Bias

It has been reported in economics times Dt 18th April 2015, under the heading- “ The NGO –Govt Showdown” The report talks about Action against – Green Peace India and an imminent crackdown on Ford foundation and Teesta Setalvad’s NGO In Gujarat. It also reports that Union Home ministry issuing show cause notices on organisations receiving foreign aid and on filing returns and their foreign contribution regulation act (FCRA) licence cancellation etc. Also Deccan Herald Dt. 19th April 2015- reports about Green Peace India facing governments wrath. All the NGOs in India are on an alert so also **CODP** in Mangaluru who has an FCRA licence.

Opportunities:

- Enough local demands
- Cooperation
- Support from religious communities
- To conduct group activities
- Community Welfare

CODP being a Christian supported NGO has been able to join hands with likeminded Hindu Organisations who wanted people to be supported in few economic activities and sought a supportive chord. It is now working out many programmes for different target groups, there is a greater cooperation, and this **CODP** wants to strengthen as they feel it is a great opportunity to move ahead in Community welfare.

Threats:

- Opposition
- Government interference
- Organisation

It feel RBI regulations on fund transfer, which has been keeping many donors away and it has hit them badly in their fund collections. They also talked about government interference in NGO activities as reported in several newspapers at all India level; they feel government interference can come in the way of their growth and activities.

CODP reported a threat they received from a some Organisation as they are supported through Mangalore Catholic Diocese

Findings of the study

It observed a peculiar problem is that people working in NGOs often do not think that they need to be managed according to basic management principals. NGO manager said that the difference between "Company's and us " is that "we (NGO types) look for money to enable us to do good things, while the business types look for things to do that will enable them to make money". Sadly, it observed that the NGO that she was working for was in the red (loss) and declining fast, due to simply, to **poor strategic management**. She was so busy "doing good things" that she was compromising her ability to do them. Surely, the first order of business for and NGO (like any other organisation) is to be in business - to survive and sustain itself: and that requires the application of sound business principles and strategic decision-making.

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Based on this study the NGOs can follow the following leadership goals:

1. A richer understanding of how to integrate organisational mission and strategy.
2. An increased confidence in their ability to lead and scale their organisation.
3. A new perspective on their organisation's potential and impact.
4. Development of a plan of action for addressing key organisational and strategic challenges.
5. A strong network of relationships with a diverse group of nonprofit leaders.

Conclusion:

NGOs as observed few are well organised as they have an international support system in place and the management style and functioning is transparent, as they have to follow the system and policies laid down by their supporting organisation. The scale and varieties of activities undertaken by the three NGOs in my study indicate that they need to be monitored well to achieve better results and they have paucity of funds, probably because of that, they have been using paternalist decision process.

Study observed they need to decentralise the decisive powers to few chosen supervisors after a thorough training to tackle localised issues. However, they can centralise decision on fund allocation through meetings conducted on a quarterly basis at the NGOs head quarters. An issue gender bias was observed, study suggests that the organisations should implement inclusive strategies and equal importance need to given to employees of opposite sex and they need to included in the strategic planning and decision-making processes.

It is a fact that every organisation including an NGO needs a strategy, if they have to effectively achieve their mission for which they are created. The senior leadership of the organisation including the visionary leaders should own the responsibility for creating and managing effective organisations. They need to develop clear concepts, principles and framework and effective models that their employees can use to formulate and deploy strategy throughout the organisation. There need to be better coordination in the internal activities and there should be better communication and alignment with the external environment, which includes recipients of benefits, donors and governmental agencies.

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